

Universität Luzern, Fakultät für Gesundheitswissenschaften und Medizin

Dissertation unter der Betreuung von PD Dr. med. Oliver Fuchs,
Luzerner Kantonsspital, Zentrum für Dermatologie und Allergologie

**Contact dermatitis: case report of an unusual
manifestation in the context of an allergy to
methylisothiazolinone**

DISSERTATION

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Sanjive Rey

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Contact dermatitis: case report of an unusual manifestation in the context of an allergy to methylisothiazolinone

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Publikation

Case report

The following case report highlights the importance of the diagnosis and treatment of contact allergies caused by isothiazolinones such as methylisothiazolinone (MI) and methylisochlorothiazolinone (MCI). The prevalence of MI/MCI-related contact allergies, a form of allergic contact dermatitis, has recently increased significantly. This is mainly due to the prevalence of MI/MCI as a preservative in a variety of products, including cosmetics, detergents and paints [1, 2]. Despite regulatory measures to limit concentrations in certain products, the risk of sensitization remains, especially in the case of occupational exposure, unlabeled products or circumvention of regulatory measures. We present a case that highlights the complex challenges and importance in the diagnosis and management of such allergies. It also highlights the need for improved education and stricter regulation of MI/MCI in products and compliance. The patient's written consent for the case report and images are available.

A 65-year-old patient was admitted to the emergency department of Zug Cantonal Hospital (ZGKS) with a suspected grade 2 anaphylactic reaction according to H. L. Müller. The symptoms, consisting of periorcular edema, facial angioedema, intense itching of the face and a subjective feeling of tightness in the throat, occurred on the fourth night in total after nightly application of a cooling mask (inserted in a fabric sleep mask) that was not directly applied to the facial skin, which the patient used to relieve chronic headaches and to darken and improve sleep at night.

The clinical picture required an initial differentiation between an allergic contact dermatitis and an anaphylactic reaction. Contact allergies in the sense of cellular-mediated type IV reactions typically manifest themselves 24-72 hours after contact with the allergen by itchy, erythematous skin lesions, often in the area of direct exposure, and more rarely also generalized.

Anaphylactic reactions in the sense of IgE-mediated type I reactions, on the other hand, typically develop (with exceptions) within minutes to a few hours after exposure and, if severe, affect several organ systems. The suspected angioedema and the feeling of tightness in the throat initially indicated systemic involvement for the colleagues working in the emergency department. We interpreted the subjective feeling of tightness in the throat as part of an anxiety reaction, as did the patient later during the assessment. The other, objectifiable symptoms of skin involvement could not initially be completely distinguished from a type I reaction, mainly due to the severity of the manifestation within the contact area in the facial region and an

obviously at least partial, incipient local generalization beyond this. In the case of contact allergic reactions, depending on the severity, there are sometimes extensive inflammatory reactions with the involvement of innate and cellular stress responses, which in some cases coordinate and also amplify each other and can therefore resemble allergic reactions such as type I reactions in their occurrence and severity [3].

After administration of oral steroids and antihistamines and inconspicuous monitoring, the patient was discharged back to his home environment. Further allergological diagnostics after six months, in particular epicutaneous testing, showed that the patient had developed a pronounced type IV sensitization to MI and the cooling element, which can be inserted into the sleep mask sealed by fabric as mentioned above, but without reacting to the other materials of the sleep mask itself (Fig. 1, Tab. 1). A direct connection between MI and the cooling mask could not yet be established with certainty, but was suspected. After research by the patient, the safety data sheet for the cooling element used in the sleep mask imported from China was identified with the help of the importer. This confirmed the suspicion that MI was used to treat the surface in a concentration of 0.0014% [4].

Cosmetics are still the most common cause of sensitization to MI/MCI. Nevertheless, their occurrence on surfaces of other materials used in everyday life, as in this example, should be considered. The case illustrates the impact of the increasing prevalence of contact allergies to these preservatives. A study by Schwensen et al. from 2017 showed that the point prevalence of sensitization to MI in various European centers was up to 6.0 % at that time, according to the annual report of the Information Association of Dermatological Clinics (IVDK) 2023, this peak has currently been exceeded, but most recently the prevalence was still 2.7 % [5, 6]. Increasing exposure to these substances has led to a sharp rise in contact allergies, which is why the need for careful monitoring and regulation of their use in consumer products is urgently indicated. [1, 5] The case illustrates the impact of this development on individual patients and the challenges in diagnosing and treating such cases, especially with regard to global production and interconnectedness in the context of trade and different labeling regulations. This case also highlights the need for careful differentiation between anaphylaxis and contact dermatitis in clinical practice and the importance of an accurate history and diagnosis. It also highlights the complexity of allergic pathophysiology and the importance of a meticulous diagnostic approach.

Fig. 1: Epicutaneous test after 48 hours; standard series according to European Baseline Series Chemotechnique S-1000: 24 (chloro)methylisothiazolinone positive (top arrow), own substances: 6 cooling pads (Cool Pack Daydream) positive (bottom arrow). In addition, the further test series also revealed a sensitization to povidone-iodine.

No.	Substance	Concentration	Reaction after				clinical relevance
			48 h	72 h	96 h	later	
1	"Nuscheli" black	pure	-	-			
2	Elastic from Maske	pure	-	-			
3	Foam from eye mask	pure	-	-			
4	Eye mask fabric	pure	-	-			
5	Fabric of eye mask rim	pure	-	-			
6	sleep mask "Cool Pack Daydream"	pure	++	+++			+

Tab 1: List of intrinsic substances with evidence of pronounced type IV sensitization to the cooling pad (Cool Pack Daydream).

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Curriculum Vitae

Sanjive Rey

27.01.1993	geboren in Luzern
2000 - 2006	Primarschule Rönimoos, Luzern (Littau)
2006 - 2009	Sekundarschule Staffeln, Luzern (Reussbühl)
2009 - 2012	Lehre Chemielaborant, Basel
2012 - 2013	Maturitätsschule für Erwachsene, Luzern (Reussbühl)
2013 - 2020	Medizinstudium an der Universität Bern
14.10.2020	Eidg. Examen Humanmedizin an der Universität Bern
01/2021 - 12/2021	Assistenzarzt Chirurgie, Zuger Kantonsspital
01/2022 - 04/2022	Dienst als Militärarzt
08/2022 - 02/2023	Assistenzarzt Chirurgie, Luzerner Kantonsspital
Seit 03/2023	Assistenzarzt Dermatologie, Luzerner Kantonsspital